

Deliverable 1.4: VISION website

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Contents

Basic information.....	3
Executive summary	4
1 Website objectives	4
2 Website structure	4
2.1 Public section.....	4
2.2 Intranet.....	4
3 Website design.....	5
3.1.1 Home	6
3.1.2 About	7
3.1.3 Partners	7
3.1.4 Trainings & Lectures	7
3.1.5 News.....	8
3.1.6 History.....	8
3.1.7 Outcomes.....	8
3.1.8 Photogallery	8
3.1.9 Collaborations	9
3.1.10 Visual identity.....	9
3.1.11 Contact	9
3.1.12 Intranet.....	9
4 Conclusion	10

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Basic information

Project title	Strategies to strengthen scientific excellence and innovation capacity for early diagnosis of gastrointestinal cancers
Project acronym	VISION
Call	H2020-WIDESPREAD-2018-2020
Topic	WIDESPREAD-03-2018
Project type	Coordination and Supporting Action (CSA)
Grant Agreement No.	857381
Nature	DEC (Website)
Dissemination level	PU (Public)

Executive summary

Deliverable D1.4 describes the structure and features of the VISION website (<http://vision.sav.sk>). The VISION website is divided into two main sections: the external (public) VISION website and internal Partners` intranet. Besides English version, the public section will also be available in Slovak, Spanish and Greek versions.

The VISION website is integrated into the structure of the website of BMC SAV – Biomedicinske centrum Slovenskej akademie vied (<http://www.biomedcentrum.sav.sk/>).

An initial external VISION website (<http://vision.sav.sk>) was launched on 15th October 2019, in project month 1. The visual identity of the website was approved by the VISION consortium during the VISION kick-off meeting on 20th November 2019. The VISION website was subsequently updated and an intranet facility added, with the website being relaunched on 15th December 2019 (project month 3).

1 Website objectives

As part of the project's dissemination strategy, the VISION website will be used as the main vehicle of communication and interaction with anyone seeking information about the VISION project, activities, news and results. The website will mainly function as a communication channel to the key stakeholders of the project (scientific community, medical experts, clinicians, policymakers including regional authorities, industry, PhD and undergraduate students, as well as the general public).

2 Website structure

The VISION project website will contribute to both external and internal communication, through an open-access external website and a password protected internal intranet.

2.1 Public section

The external website will be the 'public face' of the project. Since VISION is publicly-funded, the project website needs to provide open-access information on the project for interested parties such as the general public. The language and technical content of the website should, therefore, take into account this audience, avoiding jargon and ensuring explanations are accessible to 'non-experts'. Public section (open access) will provide basic information on the project and its significance, scientific information on gastrointestinal (GI) cancers, and related information to the general public, with constantly updated information, links to other relevant websites and an open forum for public discussion on the key topics. An integral part will be the guidelines on how to apply for participation in summer school, workshops, trainings and other actions opened for scientists in the field. This public section will also be available in Slovak, Spanish, Greek and English versions.

2.2 Intranet

The internal intranet will support internal communication between consortium partners and access will be limited to project members via the use of a password-protected site. Private project management/consortium section will be created for sharing the results among project

participants, with participants' contact information, project planning, details on meeting organisation and meeting reports, an upload area for file exchange and a closed multi-threaded forum for discussion among project participants.

3 Website design

The heading of the website contains a project logo (Fig. 1). The logo has been approved by the Partners during the VISION kick-off meeting and will be used for all communication purposes.

Figure 1. Logo of the VISION project.

The VISION website (Fig. 2) consists of several webpages grouped under the following sections:

- Home
- About
- Partners
- Trainings & Lectures
- News
- History
- Outcomes
- Photogallery
- Collaborations
- Visual identity
- Contact
- Intranet

Figure 2. The heading of the VISION website.

3.1.1 Home

The section “Home” is the first webpage appearing when clicking on the website address. It includes general information about the project. It contains acknowledgement to the financing of the project and the EU emblem (Fig. 3A and 3B).

Figure 3A. The VISION website design (English version).

ÚVOD

NAŠA MISIA

PARTNERI

NOVINKY

HISTÓRIA

VÝSLEDKY

FOTOGALÉRIA

SPOLUPRÁČA

VIZUÁLNA IDENTITA

KONTAKT

ÚVOD

Slovensko patrí ku krajinám s najvyšším výskytom zhubných nádorov tráviaceho traktu v Európe. Ide predovšetkým o kolorektálny karcinóm a karcinóm pankreasu. Napriek mnohým pokrokom v diagnostike a liečbe, predstavujú tieto ochorenia stály problém. Neustále sa zvyšuje ich incidencia a nízky počet pacientov je zachytených vo včasných štádiách, kedy je ochorenie riešiteľné štandardnými liečebnými postupmi. Včasná diagnostika je preto základom pre zvýšenie percenta prežívania pacientov a zlepšenie kvality ich života. Cieľom projektu VISION je rozšírenie spolupráce s významnými vedeckými inštitúciami, ktoré sa zaoberajú klinicky-orientovaným výskumom. Vďaka tejto spolupráci by sme chceli dosiahnuť zvýšenie kvality výskumu, prenos získaných vedeckých výsledkov do klinickej praxe a v konečnom dôsledku skorú diagnostiku a efektívnu liečbu pre pacientov s týmito ochoreniami.

Figure 3B. The VISION website design (Slovak version).

The Greek and Spanish versions of the VISION website are in process.

3.1.2 About

The section "About" includes the main objective and specific aims of the VISION project including the project structure. In addition, the members of the Steering Committee and the Scientific Advisory Board are presented here.

3.1.3 Partners

This section provides basic information about the partners including a summary of partners' expertise and link to their website together with the institutional logo.

3.1.4 Trainings & Lectures

This section will provide information about the open calls for trainings and lectures. Here, the applicants can find the list of open calls, detailed instructions how to apply, which documents

are required to be submitted together with the application (CV, Motivation letter etc.) as well as online registration for lectures.

3.1.5 News

The “News” section primarily serves as a source of information about daily activities and news within the project (Fig. 4). The section will also include upcoming events such as consortium meetings, courses, training activities etc. This section will be regularly updated. Links to articles, press releases, interviews, videos, etc. will be uploaded here.

Figure 4. The VISION Kick-off meeting.

3.1.6 History

This section will archive all the information about the actions performed within the project implementation.

3.1.7 Outcomes

Here will be presented short reports of realized activities, list of publications and project proposals relevant for VISION project will be presented.

3.1.8 Photogallery

This section will provide photo documentation from all ongoing VISION events (consortium meetings, trainings, outreach activities etc.) (Fig. 5)

HOME
ABOUT
PARTNERS
NEWS
OUTCOMES
PHOTOGALLERY
VISUAL IDENTITY
CONTACT
INTRANET

PHOTOGALLERY

Figure 5. The VISION Kick-off meeting participants.

3.1.9 Collaborations

Here will be presented all organizations together with the link to their websites that support actions organized under the VISION project and closely collaborate with the VISION partners.

3.1.10 Visual identity

Logo, project leaflet/flyer and banner will be presented here. Project leaflet/flyer and banner will be accessible – free to download.

3.1.11 Contact

Contacts for the Project Coordinator, Scientific Project Manager and Project Manager are available in this section.

3.1.12 Intranet

The VISION intranet supports internal communication on the project by allowing the sharing of information with the whole consortium in the following areas:

- Management: Consortium Agreements, the up-to-date mailing list of partners, deliverables;
- Meeting information: schedules, agendas, presentations, minutes;

- Dissemination: visual identity files and templates (timesheet, reporting, presentation templates, acknowledgement).

4 Conclusion

The VISION website layout is flexible and will be continuously updated in accordance with the project needs. In the future, we will expand the project's 'online outreach' to social media platforms. Social networking sites, such as Twitter, LinkedIn and Facebook, can be effectively targeting communication tools.